

APEER: An Interactive Cloud Platform for Microscopists to Easily Deploy Deep Learning

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ABSTRACT

APEER is a cloud platform providing an innovative and flexible development environment for exploration and visualization of various image processing applications. The goal of this framework is two-fold: (i) to provide researchers easy access to state-of-the-art Deep Learning technologies for microscopy through an intuitive workflow user interface and (ii) to allow experienced users to share their own-written modules from Python, MATLAB, Java or ImageJ Macro. APEER is freely accessible through any web browser under <https://www.apeer.com>.

Recent innovations from the many worlds of imaging, from that of the generation of unimaginably powerful electron microscopes to that of the novel super resolution fluorescent microscopy, researchers have been given the ability to visualise biological samples in much greater detail than ever before. This comes with large volumes of imaging data, meaning powerful software tools that are able to analyse this data rapidly and reliably are in high demand. Advances in Deep Learning (DL) technologies have been proven to outperform conventional image processing methods and gain popularity in different applications within life sciences for their potential to analyse large and complex data sets¹⁻³. This is evident in the current research landscape where image analysis tools are frequently developed for specific project needs. However, these tools are heavily fragmented with little to no standardisation framework and, for researchers to grasp the full potential of these technologies by applying them to their own datasets, a high degree of coding expertise is often needed. Furthermore, these models often come with complex strict hardware and software requirements, where just setting up these environments can be a hurdle in itself.

As image analysis is a frequent and important step in interpreting experimental results, reproducibility can become a challenge due to the complexity of image processing problems which require robust methods^{4,5}. While services like GitHub can partly alleviate these difficulties, image processing tasks often become too technical for an easy solution where enhancing transparency and automation levels in image analysis for researchers would be of great use. What makes a software good is its ability to satisfy the brief. However, what makes a software great is its ability to connect research fields and, more importantly, people. Various aspects, including accessibility from any device from anywhere in the world, establishing computational frameworks and generating a driving force to potentially affect policy changes that redefine the science community's standards of analysis, are a just handful of examples of what unites and promotes cross-field communication and, ultimately, large-scale research.

Here we present APEER (<https://www.apeer.com>), a versatile cloud platform to address various image processing problems designed to provide scientists who have little to no coding background easy access to advanced image processing tools (Figure 1a).

APEER comes with a Graphical User Interface (GUI) and runs as a web application to provide a fast and reliable user experience across all mainstream platforms, including laptops and mobile devices. This is achieved by exploiting computational resources provided by cloud-technologies, thereby promoting scalability. APEER functionalities are provided by independently operating self-contained modules that can be organized into workflows, streamlining the execution of multiple modules (Figure 1b). Currently, APEER comprises over 200 image processing modules and 60 pre-existing public workflows. It ranges from conventional segmentation methods (e.g. watershed, nuclei segmentation) to advanced DL models (e.g. U-Net 3D^{6,7}, StarDist⁸, ilastik⁹, Cellpose¹⁰). Implementation of complete software frameworks like SpinX is also possible¹¹.

A typical user pipeline (Figure 1c): (I) Users can upload microscopy images on their personal cloud storage provided by

APEER. (II) Most DL models require data annotations labeling the contents in a way that's recognizable to machines through computer vision. Hence, users have access to APEER's powerful in-house annotation tool to label object of interests through time and and z-slices. (III) Different DL models are available for users to train models with their own data and annotations. (IV) Once processing steps are complete, an email notification will be sent to the user. Results, including trained models and prediction results can then be viewed, downloaded to the user's machine and shared amongst peers. (V) To promote discussion, we also provide a dedicated forum. Developers also have the option to share their workflows and modules with collaborators or publish their work on the APEER platform.

Thanks to Docker technologies, we have been able to develop multiple features on our software that are of high importance for the scientific community at large. APEER utilises containerization which allows easy execution of modules that have been written in a range of popular programming languages, including Python, MATLAB, Java or ImageJ Macro. It therefore also supports mainstream DL frameworks including Tensorflow and Keras running side-by-side on the same underlying infrastructure. To achieve this, each module is encapsulated in a self-container and its specifications can be defined by a JSON file. This includes which inputs are expected by a module and which outputs it will generate. More technical details can be found on the [APEER documentation](#)¹. In addition, every docker-image is tagged, ensuring that the exact same code with its dependencies can be successfully executed at any time, thus ensuring reproducibility and longevity of the deployed software. These features are bound to ensure the much-needed development of the userbase and their ability to deploy and share their own modules on APEER to collaboratively work on the same code. Finally, APEER's ability to integrate into imaging facilities and be executed locally comes at ease, bringing users peace of mind and enabling the efficient leverage of public data and methods.

Recognizing the challenges researchers often face when it comes to microscopy and image processing, we provide with APEER a resourceful platform that bridges the gap between developers and scientists by taking advantage of cloud technologies. With APEER, our ultimate goal is to make research more cost-effective, increase efficiency and equip researchers with the tools they need to help them adapt to the increasingly complex field of image processing whilst generating reproducible research in life sciences and beyond.

Software and Hardware Availability

The platform is freely available under: <https://apeer.com>. A detailed tutorial on APEER: <https://docs.apeer.com>. The forum is accessible under: <https://forum.apeer.com>. The original source code for modules uploaded on APEER can be downloaded individually if the module developer allows.

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Contributions

These contributions follow the Contributor Roles Taxonomy guidelines: <https://casrai.org/credit/>. Conceptualization: DD, BS; Funding acquisition: BS; Project administration: BS, BF; Supervision: BS; Visualization: DD; Writing – original draft: DD, TI, ML; Writing – review & editing: all authors.

Conflict of interests

The authors declare no competing financial interests.

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Additional information

To include, in this order: **Accession codes** (where applicable); **Competing interests** (mandatory statement).

The corresponding author is responsible for submitting a [competing interests statement](#) on behalf of all authors of the paper. This statement must be included in the submitted article file.

Figure 1. Overview of APEER. (a) Schematic view of APEER’s architecture. APEER’s core is a progressive web app that support different programming languages and Deep Learning frameworks. (b) APEER functionalities operate in workflows which are organised by modules. All available workflows and modules are listed on APEER in a convenient gallery view with cover image, which allows easy navigation, search, execution and sharing. (c) A typical user pipeline on APEER to build and deploy Deep Learning models.